

A Synthesis of 3,4,5,6-Dibenzocyclohepta-1,3,5-triene-1-Carboxylic Acid

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o-Nitrobenzaldehyde was condensed with sodium β -phenylpropionate to furnish α -benzyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic acid (I; R=NO₂) according to known procedure¹. The amino compound (I; R=NH₂) on diazotisation followed by treatment with Cu-powder provided 3,4,5,6-dibenzocyclohepta-1,3,5-triene-1-carboxylic acid (II). The structure of the latter is proved by its conversion into 3,4,5,6-dibenzocyclohepta-3,5-diene-1-carboxylic acid² by reduction with sodium amalgam.

α -Benzyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic Acid (I; R=NO₂).—*o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (15 g.), sodium β -phenylpropionate (17.2 g.) and acetic anhydride (25 ml.) were heated in an oil-bath at 120° for 70 hr. The mixture was treated with an excess of 2N sodium carbonate solution (300 ml.). The alkaline solution was once washed with ether and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. α -Benzyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic acid formed colourless prisms (0.2 g.), from ethanol, m.p. 239° (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.6. C₁₆H₁₃O₄N requires C, 67.84; H, 4.59%).

α -Benzyl-*o*-aminocinnamic Acid (I; R=NH₂).—To the boiling solution of ferrous sulphate (33 g.) in water (26 ml.) was added with stirring a solution of α -benzyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic acid (4 g.) in liquor ammonia (10 cc) previously diluted with water (16 ml.) during 45 min. Ammonia was occasionally added to keep the liquid slightly alkaline. The precipitated ferric hydroxide was removed and the filtrate concentrated. This was cooled and acidified with 4N aqueous acetic acid. α -Benzyl-*o*-aminocinnamic acid (I; R=NH₂) (2.4 g.) crystallised in shining yellow needles, m.p. 140° (from ethanol) (Found: C, 75.8; H, 5.91. C₁₆H₁₅O₂N requires C, 75.88; H, 5.92%).

1. G. K. Ingold and H. A. Piggott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 2386; G. K. Ingold and C.W. Schopper *ibid.*, 1929, 449.

2. J. Kenner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 621.

3,4,5,6-Dibenzocyclohepta-1,3,5-triene-1-carboxylic Acid (II).—A solution of the preceding amino compound (3 g.) in water (78 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc. 78 ml.) was treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (5 g.) in water (20 ml.) in the cold. The resulting solution was further treated with copper powder (8 g.) in small quantity. The whole solution was then made alkaline. The finely divided copper was filtered and the solution acidified to provide (II), m.p. 170-172°. (Found: C, 81.02; H, 4.98. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.35; H, 5.08%). The saturated acid, m.p. 158° (lit.⁴ m.p. 158°) was obtained from the foregoing compound by reduction with 2.5% sodium amalgam (Found: C, 80.7; H, 5.82. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$: C, 80.67; H, 5.8%).

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